

THE MODERN NARRATIVE OF RELIGION AND THE AMBIGUOUS ASPECT OF ISLAM AND HUMANITY IN SOCIETY

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ABSTRACT

I am organizing this research article based on the premise that, despite a clear narrative of religion in our society, its practical application remains ambiguous. By "clear," I refer to the general principles and teachings of living life in every religion, particularly those of Islam, which is more enriched with logical reasoning compared to its precursor faiths. The followers of this religion possess comprehensive teachings. In this context, I assert that, despite being widely recognized, the practices of religion are not free from ambiguity. Furthermore, one of the foundational members of society, "humanity," is also grappling with helplessness. Despite the presence of clear religious teachings, individuals remain deprived of their fundamental rights and are struggling for the survival of their humanity. This research article will discuss two aspects: first, what the contemporary narrative of today's religions, especially Islam, will be; and second, the value and dignity of humanity will be highlighted. Efforts will be made to resurrect the intellectual debris of society that has been obscured by our shortcomings and negligence.

Keywords: Modern, Narrative, Religion, Ambiguous, Aspect, Islam, Humanity, Society.

INTRODUCTION

Identifying the right direction in the ups and downs of life is the greatest challenge and a significant issue of the modern world. When it comes to religion and humanity, the matter becomes even more serious, entangling itself in a puzzle that is not easy for a student like me to unravel. This is especially true in today's era, where religion is often viewed with disdain and treated as a burden, and every nuance requires interpretation and clarification as if answers should be delivered with the speed of a computer. There will be questions, demands for interpretations and explanations, and relentless efforts to find solutions to each issue, so aggressive that, in the absence of answers, one might bluntly state:

"Religion is the opiate of the people."

"Religion does not provide justification for the solutions to all problems."

"Religion forces individuals to be submissive or makes them victims."

"Religion began with the poor and the helpless and ends with them."

These are some of the theories that circulate in our society. In a way, the emergence of such questions is both natural and indicative of maturity. When there is a mind, there will be questions. Intellectual cultivation prompts inquiries, and answers will be sought from that specific class which acts as the guardian of religion in any society. Scholars, clerics, priests, pundits, rabbis, and others are often the primary targets for such questions because they are the key figures in their respective religions. Seeking answers from them is a natural process, and there seems to be no justification for expressing anger, issuing blasphemy fatwas, or attributing atheism to this inquiry. It is a historical fact that among the

custodians of religion, there has often existed a long list of the poor and the helpless. In fact, among those influenced by the initial preaching of our great Prophet Muhammad, many were either extremely poor or enslaved and oppressed individuals. Companions like Bilal Al-Habashi, Suhayb Al-Rumi, and Zayd ibn Harithah are living examples of this undeniable reality. Additionally, the king of Rome, Heraclius, asked Abu Sufyan one of the questions regarding Islam:

“Who are the majority among the followers of this (Islam)? The weak or the powerful? Abu Sufyan had replied that it was mostly the weak who followed Muhammad.” (Bukhari, 2002)

On the other hand, the Quraysh of Mecca sent Nadr bin Al-Harith and Uqbah bin Abi Mu'ayt to the Jewish tribes of Medina to gather information about Muhammad. They visited the Jews and reported that an increasing number of poor individuals were becoming supporters and like-minded followers of Muhammad. Upon hearing this, the Jews remarked that Muhammad is indeed the Messenger of Allah, and these are the very qualities we have seen in the previous scriptures. (Majlisi, 2005)

Therefore, the attraction of the poor, weak, and helpless individuals to religion is not an indication that religion is inherently irrational or irrelevant, nor that it cannot become a guiding light for humanity. Is it not a remarkable example of the authenticity and gentleness of Islam that, in the perilous society of the Arabs—where no refuge was available for a poor and helpless person—Islam emerged as a savior for them and became a remedy for their sorrows? One of the significant issues faced by humanity at that time was how to identify and affirm their humanity. Islam came as a claimant to that identity and truly provided it. It lifted individuals from the depths of despair to the heights of dignity. Negating color and caste, it transformed Bilal al-Habshi into Bilal the Muezzin and Salman Al-Farsi into Salman Al-Muhammadi. (Ibn Al-Atheer, 1390 AH) This is the enlightened aspect of religion that should receive commendation rather than criticism.

It is also a reality that when a religion receives rapid and significant acceptance, opposition from people often arises spontaneously. Subsequently, personalities, ideologies, religions, and sects emerge in opposition. Clearly, the individuals targeted by this opposition will be the oppressed. They are not powerful or supernatural beings capable of countering all forms of opposition; therefore, being

oppressed is not a weakness or inadequacy of any religion. The number of oppressed individuals within a religion is inconsequential. What matters is that there should be richness in thoughts, ideologies, and teachings. Oppression has never hindered the logical and rational foundation of any religion. In fact, I believe that the expression of oppression occurs where there is a spirit of fighting and sacrificing for what is right, while oppressors are always seeking to usurp the truth, which no discerning person can support.

The emergence of the above questions is not surprising in any way. The person of our era is reaching the peak of mental maturity. There was a time when individuals could not resolve their daily affairs, let alone delve into the intricacies of religion and the conquest of the universe. Today's individual, however, becomes constantly inquisitive and seeks answers as if they expect an instant response, much like “Google” provides immediately upon inquiry. The remarkable property of “Google” is that as soon as you type any word, you receive an instant answer. For example, if we search for the word “Buroq” (A term from the Balti language typically used to refer to people living in high and elevated mountainous areas, particularly common in the majority language of Gilgit-Baltistan, Shina), we may not find its meaning according to our common understanding. However, in Arabic, it is defined as “claps of thunder.” This is the immediate answer provided by Google, which a modern mind might not find difficult to accept. Google excels in relaying information and gossip, and it responds almost instantly as you type on the keyboard. If I were not fearful of backlash, I would certainly liken Google to a particular segment of humanity and theorize that its ability to provide swift answers and relay information is an inherited trait from that segment. This characteristic of Google—that it does not hesitate to respond and answers instantly—is its unique attribute. Now, we have similar expectations from the guardians of religion. If they exhibit even slight hesitation in answering or create a situation of ambiguity, a definitive conclusion against religion is quickly formed and it is hastily asserted that “religion is merely a construct of ancient humans created to find mental solace in the absence of answers to questions beyond their understanding.” (M. Deen, M. Mobashir, M. Shariq, 2017)

It is possible that there may be some truth to this opinion. For if those who are custodians of religion display weakness, inevitably, fingers will be pointed

toward religion itself. Religion, after all, is a silent "counterpart." It is neither authorized to engage in direct dialogue with us nor capable of responding to our questions. In such a context, is it rational or just to blame a religion and its teachings? This question undoubtedly warrants careful consideration. Therefore, I pose the following question for reflection: If religion is not the appropriate choice for modern life, what is the alternative?

Firstly, science? In which a theory attains the status of dogma in one era, only to be deemed futile and unproductive in another. A renowned scientist stated in his early life that God exists, but on his deathbed, he declared that God does not exist. (Stephen Hawking, 2020). It is also not the case that science is inherently a denier of God and religion. Many scientists have been believers in God and religion. (Clover Monsma, n.d.)

Secondly, atheism?

In which neither a creator and sovereign exists, nor is there a concept of worship and beliefs. How can we possibly accept that such a vast universe came into existence spontaneously, with no one to govern it? Why do we not observe our own world, where even the most insignificant object cannot come into being on its own? How then could such a grand universe have formed itself? There must be someone who created us all.

Thirdly, religion?

Whose teachings constantly point towards the Creator of the universe, and which has always claimed to be the salvation of humanity. Religion posits that humanity is obligated to religion both actually and potentially. In no circumstance is humanity free from obedience to religion and the concept of a creator. These are the assertions of books based on religious teachings. Particularly in the Holy Quran, there are clear commands regarding the existence of God and obedience to Him. Furthermore, one meaning of Islam is submission. If we have submitted to religion, what is the harm in becoming obedient rather than remaining objectors?

A Common Approach to Anthropology and Temperament:

I contend that our temperament, rather than mirroring our true personality, indicates a dual nature. We are not who we outwardly appear to be. Whenever we speak or harbor feelings of affection,

love, and closeness for someone, we conceal our true selves and attempt to satisfy the other person with a fabricated persona. This is why we have neither been able to cultivate genuine relationships to this day nor become exemplars of sincere affection. We have considered certain superficial matters and self-devised measures as the ultimate solution for societal progress and social survival. Why is it that centuries have passed, yet the sun of true humanity has not yet risen? This question will render many philosophical tongues speechless and leave the minds of many intellectuals without an answer. Undoubtedly, the response to this question will also become so entangled in myriad complexities that discussions will be lengthy, and even a semblance of satisfaction will never be seen. Therefore, without further prolonging the discussion, we will say that days are passing and nights are departing, and every moment cries out for our humanity. At times, our entire being has been so bitter that it has become a means of causing the death of millions of people in mere moments. (Masao Tomonaga, 2019) At times, we resolved to divide ourselves among nations and religions, engaging in mutual strife and conflict, thereby creating a chasm whose consequences future generations would be forced to bear. (Murtaza Ahmad Khan, 2022) At times, we have also pulled the ropes of sectarian bigotry, claiming that such actions could serve the cause of religion.

Ultimately, this resulted in conflict between various sects and religions. Within Islam, Shia and Sunni sects engaged in mutual strife, while in the Christian world, Protestants and Catholics maintained animosity in every aspect. It is noteworthy that contemporary Christianity emphasizes religion over sectarianism, whereas, regrettably, in the Muslim world, religion has become secondary, while sectarianism remains prevalent. The psychological disposition of contemporary Muslim society has become so fragmented that intolerance and an inequitable system are deeply entrenched.

These are the historical events at a collective level that have been highlighted. Now, let us also turn our attention to the individual aspect of human temperament, which has consistently been negative. Selected examples and events would only lengthen the discussion. For the present, a few examples (relevant to Pakistani society) will suffice to clarify the point. As we all know, the religious element is as prominent in our society as expectations are high. The shadows of religious values are deeply ingrained in people's temperament. This common societal

approach is so evident that if a person speaks even slightly against religiosity, a swift reaction ensues. Both the elite and the common have learned that: "Everything is permissible, but any attempt to criticize religion will not be tolerated. Religion is ingrained in our very being. Even if we are not religious in practice, we are devotees of the entirety and details of religion."

"This is the general attitude of Pakistani society. Everyone prefers to be a 'guardian' of religion rather than learning and practicing it. What is even more peculiar is that, despite the pervasive influence of religion in our society, the bonds of morality appear to be weakening. People possess immense intellectual capabilities, but there is a prevalent trend of not being acquainted with the true essence of that intellect. In the past decade, countless innocent girls and boys have fallen victim to this escalating and uncontrolled 'awareness'. (H. Kanwal, U. Daraz Nangiana, 2018) When the followers of a religion, whose very foundation is education and morality, deviate from the path of humanity and behave like unbridled beasts, understanding the human temperament becomes not only difficult but impossible. Can you believe that a person, seemingly decent in appearance, demeanor, and lifestyle, transforms into a monster in the next moment? When such an incident occurs, and there is nothing left but regret, we exclaim:

"Indeed! We are still in the process of understanding. We have not even learned the entire process from our existence to our survival, let alone being acquainted with the human temperament."

Considering all the aforementioned examples, I contend that throughout history, whether distant or recent, the bitter experience of failing to comprehend human temperament has persisted, and this trend continues unabated. As an illustration, I will outline three key points:

Firstly, our personality has become a separate aspect from our character.

Secondly, our temperament has deviated from our true nature and become part of another agenda.

Thirdly, our words are in complete contradiction to our actions. We act contrary to what we say.

I maintain that the intractable problem of society is the assessment of human temperament. Despite all your efforts and claims of having surpassed the limits of understanding a particular individual, and

asserting complete familiarity with their every fiber, I believe this assertion is akin to conquering America from afar (although for many, the desire to reside there far outweighs the desire to conquer it), or, for a staunchly devout individual, the annihilation of 'infidels', or, a contemporary example, considering oneself among the Mujahideen of Ghazwa-e-Hind, and so on. I offer these examples because our society's general disposition has become such that we greatly favor the world of dreams and fantasies. Each of us has established a world of illusions. Countless commentaries and thousands of pronouncements are sufficient to elucidate this temperament of ours. Consider a prominent and perpetually 'thriving' example from family life. You will distinctly perceive that despite the repeated occurrence of this example, it can still be cited as the latest instance. In our society, two crucial pillars, husband and wife, spend many springs of life together. Sometimes, their companionship lasts until death and the threshold of the grave. Can the temperament, mutual understanding, and mental harmony of these two be considered ideal? I believe that neither in the present nor in any era past has this been the case, nor will these two pillars ever cease to be in a state of mutual incomprehension. It would not be surprising if this continuity persists until the end of the world. Despite living in close proximity, these two cannot become acquainted with each other's temperament, so how is it possible to comprehend the temperament of an entire society? This is why this aspect of human life, being profoundly deep, continues to be the subject of ongoing efforts and endeavors for its comprehension. New ideas, theories, and thoughts are being formulated, contributing to the expansion of human knowledge. The expectation remains that the facet of temperament recognition will one day be mastered, and people will readily comprehend human temperament.

The Disarray of Muslim Society:

When we closely observe Muslim societies, we encounter lengthy narratives of the degrading treatment of humanity. The extent of these societies' decline can be gauged by the fact that, in some instances, there is a complete lack of shame in perpetrating heinous crimes. Murder, widespread chaos, and disorder are rampant. There is neither a trace of compassion nor any element of tolerance visible. Adopting an attitude of intolerance over trivial matters is the most prominent characteristic

of contemporary Muslim societies. Recall those times when it was incredibly easy to rob a person walking on the street in Karachi, Pakistan's largest city. There was even a set 'price' for snatching a simple mobile phone, and that price was the easy murder of a human being. The stories of blood-soaked streets are replete. Fear and terror were omnipresent. Is it conceivable that, as a Muslim, I would subject another human being to fear and panic, let alone be guilty of murdering a fellow Muslim? How could we overlook the hadith in which the great man of the universe, Prophet Muhammad, defined a Muslim as one from whose hands and tongue another Muslim is safe and secure? (Tirmidhi, 2009) Yet, after committing all sorts of atrocities, people proudly proclaim: 'Praise be to God, I am a Muslim.' A description of such 'Muslimness' is beyond my capacity to pen, but I will certainly say that we have completely forgotten the lessons of ethics and humanity under the guise of Islam. The Baldia Town factory fire was another heart-wrenching and humanity-shaming incident that spared no effort in tarnishing Karachi's peaceful (former) image. (Web Desk, 2015) Nearly three hundred people lost their lives at the hands of their fellow humans, leaving a message for those who survived:

"Indeed, if you profess to be Muslims, then first learn to be human."

Moral Decline in Muslim Society:

The most unfortunate indication is that Muslims, who identify themselves as followers of a sacred religion, suffer from a severe deficiency in morality. Along with an extreme lack of awareness among the people, the essence of human character has also disappeared. The religion that has always advocated for humanity and declared serving humanity as its guiding principle, its followers have neither learned to be ashamed nor have they demonstrated a tendency to refrain from further transgressions. The religion whose great Prophet was described in the words of God as possessing 'exalted character' (Khuluqin Azim), its adherents have fully performed the ritual of mortgaging morality in every sphere of life. Whether it is societies or institutions, countries or cities, villages or rural areas, roads or streets, none of us has strived to make the ideals of Islam practicable in every place.

Urban and Social Conundrum:

Consider urban life in Pakistan, where cities generally lack proper sanitation. How can we describe the apathy and laziness of the followers of a religion that equates cleanliness and purity with half of faith, if not as misfortune? Neither have the authorities clearly defined their responsibilities, nor have the common people and the elite taken individual responsibilities into account. When there is a widespread tendency to disregard responsibilities, then believe me, it is highly unlikely that our society will be roused by writings of this nature.

The Nexus of Criticism and Action:

The core issue is that while many of us are capable of criticism, hardly anyone desires to embody a model of practical life. In an environment where evading responsibility is commonplace, where everyone views their own obligations as a burden to be placed on someone else's shoulders, neither is the true essence of humanity apparent, nor are the laws and demands associated with humanity nurtured. The most appalling aspect is that, in such a society, the act of associating humanity with degradation is repeatedly practiced. The real purpose of this writing has also been to point out such an aspect, which may become the cause of highlighting the honor and dignity of humanity.

We are living in a settlement of human-like animals. The situation is such that celebrations are held for the murder of humanity, and the humiliation of women is viewed with pride. The cry of an oppressed person is not given heed, solely because that person is not 'like' them (in terms of tribe, ethnicity, sect, and religion). If matters were confined to this, it would have been a source of some comfort, but the tales and stories of our inhumanity extend even further. We (humans) stand at a juncture where both ends of the street are closed. That is to say, the constructive dream of the society, which was promised to us (an allusion to Adam, the 'vicegerent' of humanity), has been snatched away. Now, we merely appear as hollow effigies of humanity. Our soul has been wounded. If an assessment of human-related ethics is made from morning till evening, and from evening till the next morning, our 'funeral' would take place every day with great pomp. The very purpose (humanity) that we claim to uphold has slowly withered away. Now, only the conceit of our 'Muslimness' remains, and that too is visible in scattered fragments and as mere particles. And every

fragment presumes that the survival of today's humanity depends solely on its blessed existence, otherwise humanity would have long ago met its demise.

The fundamental element of building a society is respect for humanity. Where humans are not given the opportunity to live, where breathing becomes difficult, and where the chain of companionship and love ends, what will happen? The same thing that is happening today, and which has been indicated in the lines above. If only 'man' would reflect on his ways and realize that the primary purpose of his creation was to respect his fellow human beings, and not to become a cause of their degradation.

An individual commits an act that results in the dishonor of another person (due to a minor disagreement). For example, without causing physical harm to that person, they demean them through words and gestures. After venting their frustration through verbal assaults, peculiar gestures, and offensive language, they calmly reassure themselves: 'I am human.' And all this is happening even in those societies where 'Muslimness' is most proclaimed. While invoking the name of God and the name of Muhammad, and giving wise references from the Holy Quran, when a person also engages in those things that are strictly prohibited in religious teachings, then I wonder what is left for us to take pride in, regarding our humanity and 'Muslimness'? We must have perished on the very day when we failed to fulfill our covenant, and the first murder of humanity was committed by our own hands. Is it not a matter of extreme shame that in societies where there are claimants to Islam, it is humanity that is in the most precarious state?

I will not narrate events and observations. I am only laying bare certain facts based on analysis. The West, which learned to be civilized from the ethos of Islam, at least now has sentiments of compassion for its own religious and sectarian brethren. Even when they conspire, they do not perpetrate sectarian and religious killings. We, on the other hand, have concealed true 'Muslimness' and paradise in the hereafter within our mutual killings and destruction. Alas, our 'Muslimness' is not free from the performance of a few rituals and a modicum of human service.

Another individual spends their entire life plotting conspiracies against others. If, by giving a little breadth to the lexical scope, I was to title this act 'hypocrisy', then perhaps it would be the best

interpretation of today's society. This act (hypocrisy) can be observed at every step. When face-to-face, slogans of servility are raised, and when out of sight, fifty kinds of obscenities spontaneously erupt. What should I say in the interpretation of this act, when an entire chapter (Surah Al-Munafiqun) exists in the Holy Quran itself? The only issue is that this Surah has never settled in our hearts. We may have recited it outwardly, but its meanings and implications have never been heeded. It is possible that this Surah applies entirely to many of us.

There is also a third individual who does not consider killing a human being a disgrace at all. It has become common practice to shower bullets on one's opponents in the name of religion and family. Unfortunately, this entire act is also being carried out in the name of religion. A person who professes the kalima (the words of affirmation of belief in God and the Prophet) is killed merely because they adhere to a different sectarian orientation. Whereas, before sect, they are a human being, and religion has guaranteed the sanctity of human life. In the second stage, they are a Muslim, and a Muslim is precisely the one from whose hands and tongue another Muslim is safe. It is only in the third stage that sectarian affiliation comes into play.

Conclusion:

Religion today often acts as a facile remedy for modern human concerns. It has become a significant tool employed in various matters, sometimes even misused. When an individual's personality adopts religion merely as a weapon, this can be immensely dangerous and detrimental to humanity. Globally, and particularly in Pakistan, numerous incidents of violence under the guise of religion—specifically killings carried out in its name—are starkly evident before us. Moreover, when examining the current deplorable state of society, it becomes apparent that sectarianism has proliferated widely. The practice of ruthless intolerance toward opposing sects has become commonplace. The tradition of tolerance and social coexistence, which once fostered harmony, has already diminished. Now, in many cases, violence and murder are considered the only solutions to sectarian conflicts. Given this context, one must question the role and utility of scholars—be they religious clerics, preachers, muftis, or jurists—who seem to perpetuate this cycle of intolerance. What value do such scholars possess when they endorse exclusion and encourage hate? What kind of scholar advocates

violence by interpreting religious teachings as justification for killing? It is crucial to recognize that the preservation of humanity fundamentally depends on mutual love, respect, sanctity, and dignity. True religious guidance should uphold these universal values rather than undermine them.

Research Methodology:

This research article has been completed using a narrative research methodology, focusing solely on observation without referencing any historical context. It is hoped that this will clarify an important aspect of religion and humanity.

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